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A Stylistic Analysis of the Distinctive Features in the Designers" Use of Vocabulary Elements in Suakin Architecture

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Abstract

The study was a stylistic analysis of the distinctive features in the designers" use of vocabulary element in Suakin Architecture. The corpus for the study consisted of four buildings selected from different Suakin Architectures. The result of the study revealed that primary elements are prevalent which serve as extension of the ideas in the secondary elements. There also abound minor elements which are used by designers to generate logical common features and step by step presentation of ideas. The examiners finds them easy to understand since they convey only single idea. Mashrobiyahs (Roshan) were as well noted as common syntactic features in the designers" use of vocabulary element. Through the use of Mashrobiyahs (Roshan), designers supply additional information to what obtains in the primary elements either by adding secondary elements before the primary elements or after it. Generic spatial relations therefore were used as joining or linking devices. The designers based on the outcome of the study used intermixed styles (Conceptual style & type) to convey their ideas to the viewers.

Keywords: Stylistic, Distinctive-Features, Designers, Vocabulary, Element, Suakin Architecture